

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>

THE FINANCIAL STRATEGY OF THE ORGANIZATION AS A FACTOR OF ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE LONG TERM

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ФИНАНСОВАЯ СТРАТЕГИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ДОЛГОСРОЧНОЙ ПЕРСПЕКТИВЕ

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TASHKILOTNING MOLIYAVIY STRATEGIYASI UZOQ MUDDATLI ISTIQBOLDA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH OMILI SIFATIDA

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abstract

The article considers the issue of improving the financial strategy of the enterprise in terms of ensuring economic security, acting as a long-term planning tool.

аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос совершенствования финансовой стратегии предприятия с точки зрения обеспечения экономической безопасности, выступающей в качестве инструмента долгосрочного планирования.

annotatsiya

Maqolada uzoq muddatli rejalashtirish vositasi sifatida ishlaydigan iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash nuqtai nazaridan korxonaning moliyaviy strategiyasini takomillashtirish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Keywords:

Technological innovations, social programs, economy, environmental economics.

Ключевые слова:

технологические инновации, социальные программы, экономика, экономика окружающей среды.

Kalit so'zlar:

texnologik yangiliklar, ijtimoiy dasturlar, iqtisodiyot, ekologik iqtisodiyot.

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The modern economy is a system of production, distribution and consumption of goods and services, which is based on the use of modern technologies, innovations and global connections.

The modern economy is characterized by a high degree of specialization, international trade and flexibility in adapting to changes.

The emergence of the digital economy.

Technological innovations of recent decades, especially in the field of information and communication technologies, have led to the emergence of the digital economy. The digital economy is based on the use of computer networks, the Internet, software and data to create, distribute and use information and services. This has opened up new opportunities for businesses and consumers, such as e-commerce, online platforms and digital services.

Technological innovations and their impact on business.

Technological innovations such as artificial intelligence, process automation, robotics and big data have significantly changed the way businesses are produced and organized. They allow you to automate routine tasks, increase production efficiency, improve product quality and create new types of goods and services. Technological innovations stimulate economic growth and competitiveness of enterprises.

Globalization and international trade.

The impact of globalization on the economy.

Globalization is the process of integrating the economies of different countries through the expansion of international trade and the free movement of capital, goods, services and people. Globalization has both positive and negative consequences for the economy. On the one hand, it promotes the expansion of markets and access to new opportunities. On the other hand, globalization can lead to inequality, job losses and negative environmental impacts.

Pros and cons of open markets.

Open markets, which are one of the manifestations of globalization, have their advantages and disadvantages. Benefits include access to a wide range of goods and services, stimulating competition, innovation and improving quality. However, open markets can also create risks for small and vulnerable industries, increase dependence on external suppliers and lead to inequality in income distribution.

Changes in the labor market and new forms of employment.

The emergence of a gig economy and a platform workforce.

The modern economy is characterized by changes in the labor market. One of these trends is the emergence of the concert economy, which is an economy of temporary and independent employment. Employees in the gig economy perform tasks

based on contracts or through online platforms such as taxi services or freelancer platforms. This creates new opportunities for entrepreneurship, but also raises issues in the field of social protection and workers' rights.

The impact of automation and artificial intelligence on workplaces.

Automation of processes and the development of artificial intelligence have a significant impact on workplaces. Some professions and types of work can be replaced by automated systems and robots. At the same time, technology creates new jobs that require special skills in the development and maintenance of new technologies. This requires training and retraining of the workforce.

The role of the state in the modern economy.

Policy of regulation and stimulation of the economy.

The state plays an important role in the modern economy through the policy of regulation and stimulation of economic activity. Regulation can be aimed at protecting consumer rights, ensuring competition in the market, regulating the financial system and controlling the use of natural resources. The State can also take measures to stimulate economic growth by investing in infrastructure, science and education.

Social protection and social programs.

The modern economy also includes a social component. The State can provide social protection and social programs to ensure social justice and support low-income segments of the population. Such programs may include medical care, unemployment benefits, pensions and other social support measures.

Sustainable development and environmental economics.

Conscious consumption and environmental innovation.

In the context of growing environmental problems and climate change, conscious consumption and environmental innovation are becoming increasingly important. The modern economy strives for more efficient use of resources, reduction of emissions and development of environmentally friendly technologies. Consumers and businesses are increasingly interested in products and services that take into account the interests of the environment.

The impact of climate change on the economy.

Climate change has a direct impact on the economy, causing environmental, economic and social consequences. Extreme weather conditions can affect agriculture, energy production, infrastructure and tourism. At the same time, the fight against climate change opens up new opportunities for environmental innovation and the development of an ecological economy.

Conclusion

The modern economy is a complex system in which technology, globalization, a changing labor market, the role of the state and sustainable development play an important role. Technological innovations and the digital economy are changing the way businesses are produced and organized. Globalization opens up new markets and requires adaptation. The changing labor market requires new approaches to employment and social protection. The role of the State is to regulate and stimulate the economy, as well as to ensure social justice. Sustainable development and the ecological economy are becoming increasingly important in the context of climate change and environmental problems.

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